

SP-RAN: Self-paced Residual Aggregated Network for Solar Panel Mapping in Weakly Labelled Aerial Images

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Abstract—With the rapid development of solar distribution, solar panel mapping is becoming increasingly valuable to decision-makers. Weakly supervised methods have been developed to reduce the cost in training sample collection, and the most successful ones follow the alternative training scheme, which first generates coarse object localizations as pseudo labels (PLs) and then utilizes these PLs to train an end-to-end network for object extraction. As remote sensing images are typically characterized by multiple occurrences of objects and complicated background, the alternative training scheme suffers from low mapping accuracy and deficient boundary maintenance due to the varying quality of PLs. In this paper, we focus on addressing these problems by adaptively adjusting the contributions of quality-varying PLs and propose a novel self-paced residual aggregated network (SP-RAN) for solar panel mapping. Specifically, with the initial PLs generated by gradient-weighted class activation mapping, a residual aggregated network is designed for target mapping with a special consideration for the capability in producing complete and well-shaped mapping results. Considering the inconsistent quality of PLs, an effective confidence-aware (CA) loss is developed to emphasize the contribution of high-quality PLs and alleviate the negative impacts brought by the bad-quality ones in the training phase. Moreover, to concentrate on boundary maintenance, a novel self-paced label correction (SP-LC) strategy is proposed to selectively update PLs by considering their reliability. Extensive experimental comparison with state-of-the-art methods and ablation study on the GSM-ACT and GSM-BRIS data sets demonstrate the superiority of the proposed method.

Index Terms—Remote sensing, weakly supervised learning, self-paced learning, residual aggregated network, object mapping.

I. INTRODUCTION

AS the most popular and dominant type of solar power technology, solar photovoltaic (PV) sees a rapid growth globally in the past decades [1]. Despite the environmental and economic benefits, the significant increase in solar PV deployment, especially small-scale solar installations influences the electricity grids behavior greatly due to the presence of varying loads and network conditions [2, 3]. Monitoring solar deployment including locations, sizes, and power capacity not only helps minimize safety risks but also aids the government and electricity companies in gaining better insights into solar energy utilization.

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Fig. 1. Different levels of supervision. (a) Training sample. (b) Pixel-wise labels. (c) Scribble-based labels. (d) Image-level labels.

Automatic solar panel mapping has been investigated in recent years, mostly by applying machine learning algorithms to high-resolution remote sensing images (RSIs). Early works followed the general rules in supervised object extraction [4–6], which consist of two main phases: 1) data representation and feature learning; 2) classifier selection and training. Handcrafted features descriptors including local color statistics [5], and Gabor energy filter [7] were utilized to produce feature representation and then traditional classifiers such as support vector machine (SVM) [4] and random forests [5] were trained with the generated feature vectors to locate solar panels with sliding windows. The discriminative power of specially designed features and classifiers plays a key role in the success of these approaches.

Nowadays, convolutional neural networks (CNNs), as one of the most prevalent deep learning techniques [8], have achieved promising results in the field of solar panel mapping. Malof et al. [9] utilized the VGG net [10] as a detector to determine the existence of solar panels in small square patches. Yuan et al. [11] considered solar panel mapping as a semantic segmentation task, and proposed a CNN-based method to produce pixel-wise classification. Later on, modified versions of classical deep network architectures [12–14] were proposed to generate dense mapping results. Wang et al. [12] introduced SegNet [15] to produce dense predictions of PV arrays' locations and sizes. Similarly, Castello et al. [13] applied a CNN in the shape of U-net [16] to discover the rooftop solar installations. Some researchers observed that traditional machine learning algorithms and CNN-based approaches have complementary advantages in identifying true positives and true negatives, respectively, and attempted to develop hybrid methods for accurate identification [17, 18].

Most existing CNN-based mapping methods require training samples with accurate pixel-wise annotations in the training phase, which is prohibitively human labor-intensive, especially

1 in remote sensing tasks. To reduce the labeling workload,
2 weakly supervised learning (WSL) [19] resorts to weak anno-
3 tations for supervision, such as image-level tags and scribble-
4 based labels, which are much easier to obtain. WSL-based
5 methods, however, are very challenging as accurate location
6 and shape cues are expected to be inferred from weak an-
7 notations such as Figure 1 (c) and (d). They usually suffer
8 from missing objects, ambiguous outlines of the detected
9 objects, and incomplete or over prediction. To minimize the
10 gap between weakly and fully supervision, most existing
11 methods leveraged an alternative training scheme [20–24]:
12 weakly supervised object localization methods such as class
13 activate mapping (CAM) [25] and gradient-weighted CAM
14 (Grad-CAM) [26] are first utilized to discover discriminative
15 but coarse regions of the objects; then, with generated regions
16 employed as ‘fake’ labels, i.e., pseudo labels (PLs), end-to-end
17 networks are trained to discover the objects in completeness.
18 Saliency cues [24, 27], boundary information [23, 28], and
19 conditional random field (CRF)-based consistency [29–31]
20 were also exploited as additional information to help find the
21 whole object extent. To take advantage of dynamic supervi-
22 sion, label updating strategy [20, 32] was also incorporated to
23 find sharp edges for the detected objects.

24 For remote sensing images (RSIs), learning from weakly an-
25 notated samples can be more difficult since RSIs are typically
26 characterized by a sparser distribution of objects, ambiguous
27 boundaries due to the limited spatial resolution, and compli-
28 cated background. Considering these characteristics, insightful
29 works [33–38] have been proposed in the literature to re-
30 duce background interference and improve accuracy. Recently,
31 WSL-based methods with image-level annotations have been
32 intensively investigated [39–42] since the image-level label is
33 one of the most efficient types of weak labels, indicating the
34 existence of objects belonging to a certain class in the image.
35 Hierarchical feature representation [39], curriculum learning
36 [42, 43], and attention mechanism [40] have been actively
37 studied and combined with the alternative training scheme to
38 further improve the performance. Without any supervision of
39 actual panel outlines, Yu et al. [44] developed the first weakly
40 supervised method specially designed for solar panel mapping,
41 named ‘DeepSolar’, in which Inception-v3 [45] and CAM are
42 incorporated to obtain integral objects in completeness. Zhang
43 et al. [32] proposed to generate PLs with Grad-CAM [26], and
44 a novel label correction strategy was proposed to refine the
45 mapping results iteratively.

46 Despite the efforts made in improving the performance, the
47 alternative training scheme faces two problems. The first one
48 is how to avoid the negative impacts resulted from the bad-
49 quality PLs given by the weakly supervised object localization.
50 Currently, most existing methods rely on CAM and Grad-
51 CAM to produce the initial localization maps, which only
52 correspond to the most discriminative part of the objects.
53 Inaccuracy of such PLs misleads the model training as the
54 network optimizes over mislabeled pixels [31], leading to
55 the unsatisfactory performance in mapping accuracy. Partic-
56 ularly, the quality of PLs varies greatly as the background
57 changes [46, 47]. Due to the inability of CAM and Grad-
58 CAM to locate multiple instances appearing in an image,

the situation would be worse, and bad-quality PLs would do
great harm to the model training. The second problem is how
to avoid partial prediction and produce the mapping results
with precise shapes. Due to the coarse PLs employed, weakly
supervised methods generally predict the most discriminative
object regions and present a weak ability to maintain well-
defined boundaries. Label updating has been revealed as
an effective way to improve object completeness [48, 49]
as well as boundary maintenance [24] via making the PLs
approaching the actual object outlines progressively. However,
most existing label updating strategies update all the PLs in
the training phase and omit the varying quality of the initial
PLs, which may introduce new falsely-labeled pixels and lead
to error accumulation.

To address these problems, we propose a self-paced residual
aggregated network (SP-RAN) for weakly supervised solar
panel mapping by using a limited number of training data at
image-level and a large number of unlabeled data. Instead of
blindly trusting the initial PLs, SP-RAN focuses on empha-
sizing the contribution of high-quality PLs and reducing negative
impacts brought by the bad-quality ones in the training phase.
As illustrated in Figure 2, the proposed method starts from
self pixel labeling to generate initial PLs with an image-level
classification network. Then, treating these labels as training
samples with uncertainty, residual aggregated network (RAN)
with an effective confidence-aware (CA) loss is trained with
a proposed self-paced label correction (SP-LC) strategy to
selectively update the PLs and boost the model performance
progressively. Moreover, a large number of unlabeled data are
automatically labeled by the self pixel labeling process and
added into the model training to improve the generalization
ability. The well-trained RAN is then used to produce the
mapping results. The main contributions of this paper are
summarized below:

(1) To avoid partial prediction, an effective confidence-
aware loss is proposed to train the RAN by dynamically
adjusting the contribution of PLs with varying qualities. The
confidence given by the image-level classification network is
used to quantify the quality of the PLs. Instead of labelling
PLs into a binary case of good and bad, the confidence-
aware loss emphasizes the contribution of high-quality ones
and suppresses the bad-quality ones based on their quality
scores.

(2) A novel self-paced label correction strategy is designed
to minimize the negative effect from irrelevant surroundings
when approaching sharp object outlines during the iterative
training. Instead of updating the entire PLs set at once, SP-LC
starts with the least ambiguous PLs first, and considers the rest
progressively. Selected PLs at each round will be updated by
combining the current output with a morphological procedure,
to minimize the error accumulation in the iteration. With
progressively corrected labels, the model becomes increasingly
reliable and approaches actual object outlines.

(3) The design of RAN considers the merits of feature
pyramid network (FPN) and residual aggregated blocks. FPN
is adopted as the backbone as it has a significant advantage
in localizing varying-size objects accurately by fully utilizing
multi-scale feature representation. In the bottom-up path of

Fig. 2. Flowchart of the self-paced residual aggregated network (SP-RAN).

the RAN, the residual aggregated block (RAB) is further incorporated to preserve abundant spatial details for outline recovery.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we introduce the self-paced residual aggregated network, and experimental results are reported in Section III. Finally, the conclusion is given in Section IV.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this section, the proposed self-paced residual aggregated network will be presented in detail. As shown in Figure 2, the SP-RAN is composed of three steps: self pixel labeling from image-level supervision, residual aggregated network for target mapping, and self-paced label correction strategy. The purpose of the first step is to generate initial PLs from image-level annotations with the aid of a well-trained classification network and Grad-CAM. Then, the second step aims to produce initial mapping results with the proposed residual aggregated network trained by the confidence-aware loss function. In the last step, the self-paced label correction strategy is proposed to selectively update PLs in a self-paced manner. Unlabeled data are also labeled and added into model training.

A. Self Pixel Labeling From Image-level Supervision

To obtain pixel-wise labels from image-level annotations, we utilize an image-level classification network and Grad-CAM to provide initial object localization. We first adopt the VGG16 net as the backbone to train a classification network, and the Grad-CAM is then leveraged to provide class activation maps, which are subsequently transformed into binary masks via Otsu thresholding. Figure 3 shows the flowchart of label generation from image-level supervision.

In our work, the provided image-wise label indicates whether or not there are targets in the image (positive or negative samples). Then the classification network is trained

to solve a binary classifications problem. VGG16 net [10] was proposed by Simonyan et al., which contains 13 convolutional layers, five max-pooling layers, three fully connected (FC) layers, and finally a soft-max layer. All the convolutional layers have a small 3×3 receptive field, 1-pixel stride, and 1-pixel padding, followed by a rectified linear unit (Relu) to increase non-linearity. Each max-pooling layer with stride 2 is carried out over a 2×2 window, separating the convolutional layers into five blocks. For the classification network, we alter the fully connected layers in the VGG16 net to 256 and 2 channels before the soft-max activation to make it suitable for the binary classification problem. The 2-dimension output of the classification network is the probabilities of the input sample belonging to positive or negative cases, respectively. The cross-entropy loss is utilized to train the classification network. Here, we use $\mathbf{F}_{i,q}^k$ to denote the k^{th} channel in the feature maps produced by i^{th} convolutional layer of the q^{th} block in the classification network.

Then, Grad-CAM takes the feature maps produced by the third convolutional layer in the fourth block in the classification network as the input to generate class activation maps. Denote the Rectified Linear Unit as $Relu$. The gradient of the classification score $f(\mathbf{I}; \Theta)_c$ for class c to $\mathbf{F}_{i,q}^k$ is first calculated, and the global average pooling, i.e., GAP is subsequently used to generate the weights as given in Eq.(1). After each channel's feature map is weighted by its weight $\hat{w}_{i,q,c}^k$, the sum leads to the final class activation map $\mathbf{M}_{i,q,c}$ (as shown in Eq.(2)).

$$\hat{w}_{i,q,c}^k = GAP\left[\frac{\partial f(\mathbf{I}; \Theta)_c}{\partial \mathbf{F}_{i,q}^k}\right], \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_{i,q,c} = Relu\left\{\sum_{k=1} \hat{w}_{i,q,c}^k \cdot \mathbf{F}_{i,q}^k\right\}, \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3. Flowchart of self pixel-wise label generation from image-level supervision.

where $\mathbf{I} \in \mathbf{R}^{H \times W \times C}$ is the input image with the size of $H \times W \times C$, Θ represents the parameter set of the classification network.

After obtaining the class activation map for the foreground class, i.e. solar panels, the Otsu segmentation method is used to produce binary masks, which are subsequently taken as initial PLs in the target mapping network.

B. Residual Aggregated Network for Target Mapping

When alleviating the reliance on image-wise annotations, weakly supervised object segmentation has three major challenges: (1) missing objects due to large appearance variations, (2) ambiguous outlines of the detected objects, and (3) incomplete prediction or over prediction. The design of RAN is to meet these challenges. To address the first challenge, we adopt FPN as the backbone of the target mapping network, as FPN has a significant advantage in localizing varying-size objects accurately by fully utilizing multi-scale feature representation [50]. However, supervised by coarse and inaccurate PLs, FPN exhibits a deficient ability to avoid partial prediction and preserve object outlines. To tackle the second challenge, RABs are incorporated with FPN to preserve abundant spatial details for precise outline recovery. Finally, to extracting the object as a whole, we propose a new confidence-aware loss, which improves the object completeness via suppressing the negative influence brought by the training samples with low-quality PLs. The architectures of the proposed RAN and RAB are presented in Figure 4.

1) *Residual aggregated block*: If a deep CNN is built by stacking consecutive convolutional layers or multiple residual blocks (RBs), features produced by the former layer are passed to the deeper layers sequentially, which means local features generated by preceding layers or blocks can hardly propagate to the end of the network. Hence, local information that needs to be preserved makes very limited contributions to the training process of the entire network as well as the final output, which inevitably leads to performance degradation. This is particularly the case for tasks requiring well preserved spatial details and object outlines.

The residual aggregated block is motivated by the residual feature aggregation framework [51], which is originally

proposed for image super-resolution. Similar to the residual feature aggregation framework, RAB makes the most of the local residual features by propagating low-level residuals of all the proceeding RBs to the end of the block. As shown in Figure 4, each RAB contains two stacked residual blocks and two convolutional layers with 3×3 kernel and 1-pixel stride. The residual features of the two RBs are concatenated directly with the output of the second RB after the first convolutional layer and then sent to the last convolutional layer, after which the channel of the feature maps doubles in number.

Denote the input and output of the j^{th} residual block in RAB as \mathbf{R}_j^{in} , and $\mathbf{R}_j^{\text{out}}$, where $j = 1, 2$. The output of the first RB is sent to the second RB as the input. The output of the RAB can be calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{Q}_j = \text{Conv}_3(\text{Conv}_3^*(\mathbf{R}_j^{\text{in}})), j = 1, 2, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_j^{\text{out}} = \mathbf{Q}_j + \mathbf{R}_j^{\text{in}}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{B}^{\text{out}} = \text{Conv}_3^*(\text{Concat}[\mathbf{Q}_1, \mathbf{Q}_2, \text{Conv}_3^*(\mathbf{R}_2^{\text{out}})]), \quad (5)$$

where Conv_3^* and Conv_3 represent a single 3×3 convolutional layers with and without *Relu*, respectively. \mathbf{Q}_j is the residual feature generate by the j^{th} residual block in RAB. $\text{Concat}[\cdot]$ denotes the concatenate operation.

2) *Residual aggregated network*: Following the FPN architecture, RAN is constructed in an encoder and decoder manner, with a shallow feature extraction module, a bottom-up path, and a top-down path with skip connections linking the two paths. In the bottom-up path, four RABs are stacked, with a max-pooling operation applied before each block. In the top-down path, coarse but semantically strong feature maps are first up-sampled, and then merged with high-resolution but low-level feature maps generated by the corresponding blocks in the bottom-up path via skip connections. The network architecture of RAN is detailed as follows:

Given the input image \mathbf{I} , two separate 3×3 convolutional layers with each followed by the *Relu* are first utilized to produce the initial features \mathbf{F}_0 , which is then sent to the bottom-up path.

$$\mathbf{F}_0 = \text{Conv}_3^*(\text{Conv}_3^*(\mathbf{I})), \quad (6)$$

The bottom-up path is composed of four repeated application of 2×2 max-pooling operation for downsampling and RAB blocks. At each RAB block, we double the number of feature channels. The output of $(p-1)^{\text{th}}$ RAB is first downsampled by a 2×2 max-pooling operation and then fed to the p^{th} RAB as the input. The output of the p^{th} RAB can be written as follows:

$$\mathbf{B}_p^{\text{out}} = \mathcal{R}_p[\downarrow \mathbf{B}_{p-1}^{\text{out}}], \quad (7)$$

where \downarrow denotes the 2×2 max-pooling operation. $\mathcal{R}_p[\cdot]$ denotes the feed-forward propagation of p^{th} RAB block.

In the top-down path, every step contains a 3×3 convolutional layer with 1-pixel stride, followed by the *Relu*, and a 2×2 up convolutional layer (up conv layer) with 2-pixel stride that halves the number of feature channels. To enhance high-level features with high-resolution features, skip connections are utilized to make element-wise addition of

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the proposed RAB and RAN for target mapping.

corresponding feature maps from the bottom-up and the top-down path. Before the addition, feature maps from the bottom-up path undergoes a 1×1 convolutional layer to reduce channel dimensions. Three extra successive 3×3 convolutional layers with 1-pixel stride are appended to reduce the aliasing effect of up-sampling operation and pixel-wise addition. Finally, a 1×1 convolutional layer with soft-max activation is added to produce the final results.

3) *Confidence-aware Loss*: Although Grad-CAM provides reasonable object location cues, it has a limited ability to capture multi-occurrence of objects and usually presents incomplete and over prediction. Training target mapping network with quality-varying PLs may lead to severe confusion and produce partial prediction only covering the most discriminative regions. Thus, how to measure the quality of PLs and emphasize the contributions of high-quality ones is crucial. Instead of only selecting high-quality samples for training and omitting bad-quality ones, we propose a confidence-aware loss and adjust the contribution based on the quality scores produced by the image-level classification network. Specifically, the confidence-aware loss is composed of three parts: weighted cross-entropy, the gated CRF regularizer, and confidence weighting.

Weighted cross-entropy. Generally, solar panels belong to the minor class compared to other major urban classes in the background of aerial images. To mitigate the influence of the imbalance between the fore- and background, we use weighted cross-entropy L_{wce} instead of cross-entropy as the first term in the confidence-aware loss (as Eqs. (8) and (9) show):

$$L_{wce} = -\sum (\alpha \cdot \mathbf{G} \cdot \log(\mathbf{f}_0) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot (1 - \mathbf{G}) \cdot \log(\mathbf{f}_1)), \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{N - N_{fore}}{N}, \quad (9)$$

where N_{fore} is the number of pixels belonging to the foreground in the ground-truth \mathbf{G} . N is the total number of pixels in the images. \mathbf{f}_0 and \mathbf{f}_1 are the first and second channel in the final output, respectively.

Gated CRF regularizer. To make the mapping network concentrate on the object boundaries with background noise, the gated CRF loss [30] is introduced as the regularizer term.

Inspired by the classical CRF model, gated CRF loss calculates the pair-wise energy term $\psi_{x,y}$ in a $r \times r$ local neighborhood window Ω_r , which measures the feature-wise similarity with pair-wise potential $k(\cdot, \cdot)$:

$$\psi_{x,y}(\mathbf{f}) = \mu(\mathbf{f}_x, \mathbf{f}_y)k(\mathbf{V}_x, \mathbf{V}_y), \quad (10)$$

$$\mu(\mathbf{f}_x, \mathbf{f}_y) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \mathbf{f}_x = \mathbf{f}_y \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (11)$$

where μ is the class compatibility matrix. \mathbf{f} is the output of the mapping network. \mathbf{f}_x and \mathbf{f}_y are the output at position x and y , respectively. \mathbf{V}_x and \mathbf{V}_y are the feature vectors for pixels at position x and y , respectively.

In this paper, we adopt the Pott's class compatibility model and the contrast-sensitive two-kernel potential, which combines color feature and spatial feature into a 5-D feature vector for color-proximity similarity. The two-kernel potential utilized in this work is shown as follows:

$$k(\mathbf{V}_x, \mathbf{V}_y) = w^{(1)} \exp\left(-\frac{|\mathbf{P}_x - \mathbf{P}_y|^2}{2\theta_1^2} - \frac{|\mathbf{S}_x - \mathbf{S}_y|^2}{2\theta_2^2}\right) + w^{(2)} \exp\left(-\frac{|\mathbf{P}_x - \mathbf{P}_y|^2}{2\theta_3^2}\right), \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{P}_x and \mathbf{P}_y denotes the spatial positions of locations x and y , respectively. \mathbf{S}_x and \mathbf{S}_y denotes the spatial feature vectors in location x and y , respectively. $w^{(1)}$ and $w^{(2)}$ are the weights for controlling the influence of the two kernels. θ_1 , θ_2 , and θ_3 control the degrees of nearness and similarity.

After measuring the total energy over Ω_r , L_{crf} can be obtained:

$$L_{crf} = \sum_x \sum_{y \in \Omega_r(x) \setminus x} \psi_{x,y}(\mathbf{f}). \quad (13)$$

Confidence weighting. To adjust the contribution of PLs with varying qualities, we employ the classification score given by the classification network as the confidence. Training samples with high confidences are supposed to contain clear and easy-to-learn objects while those with low confidences are more like to contain ambiguous and hard-to-discriminate targets. After weighting the WCE loss and the gated CRF regularizer term with the classification score, the confidence-aware loss can be computed as follows:

$$L = \sum_m f(\mathbf{I}; \Theta)_{c=1}^{(m)} \cdot (L_{wce}^{(m)} + \lambda L_{crf}^{(m)}), \quad (14)$$

where $L_{wce}^{(m)}$ and $L_{crf}^{(m)}$ are the WCE loss and the gated CRF regularizer for m^{th} training sample. $f(\mathbf{I}; \Theta)_{c=1}^{(m)}$ is the classification score of the foreground class, i.e., $c = 1$ for m^{th} training sample. λ balances the WCE loss and the gated CRF regularizer term.

C. Self-paced Label Correction

Compared with training the mapping network with fixed PLs, supervision with progressively corrected PLs has been revealed more beneficial to model training. Although some criteria based on CRF, region growing, etc. have been incorporated, label updating operation, however, may cause error

accumulation as it may introduce false-labeled pixels. Hence, how to avoid over correction or under correction has been a problem worthy of attention. As solar panels usually have similar colors with rooftops and exhibit ambiguous edges, resorting to CRF, saliency cues or boundary information may not be helpful in this case.

Motivated by the observations, we propose an effective self-paced label correction strategy, which first utilizes self-paced learning to select training samples, whose PLs are close enough to the output of the currently trained model. These PLs are considered high-quality and reliable ones. Then, the PLs of the selected training samples are corrected by processing the network output with a morphological procedure. With a gradually improved threshold for self-paced learning and model capability, a growing number of training samples and corresponding PLs will be selected and corrected, which will help develop a reliable model with enough robustness against noisy PLs. Despite sharing similar idea of label update with Ren's work [48] and Lin's work [49], the proposed SP-LC module has two distinct features: instead of discovering missing proposals at instance level, SP-LC operates at an image level and is designed to alleviate the potential errors, i.e., newly introduced false 'labels' resulted from the label correction operation via considering the degree of confidence and the level of quality of the samples; furthermore, SP-LC module does not require any changes to the network architecture, so it can be easily plugged into any backbone networks during training.

Self-paced learning [52, 53] is a recently proposed learning paradigms aiming to start the learning process with easy samples and then gradually add hard samples into training. Sharing the similar concept to curriculum learning [54], self-paced learning adjusts the learning pace according to the model ability by adding a new regularization term to the learning objective, shown as follows:

$$\min_{\Phi, \mathbf{v} \in [0,1]^n} \mathbb{E}(\Phi, \mathbf{v}; \delta) = \sum_{m=1}^n v_m L(\mathbf{G}^{(m)}, g(\mathbf{I}^{(m)}; \Phi)) + f(\mathbf{v}, \delta), \quad (15)$$

where $L(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the loss function for the mapping network. $g(\mathbf{I}^{(m)}; \Phi)$ denotes the output of the mapping network with parameter set Φ for m^{th} training sample. $\mathbf{G}^{(m)}$ is the label for m^{th} training sample. $\mathbf{v} = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n]$ is the weights indicating the training samples' learning difficulties. n is the total number of training samples.

$f(\mathbf{v}, \delta)$ is the self-paced regularizer controlling the selection of the training samples according to the threshold δ . In this paper, we employ a simple but effective l_1 -norm regularizer, which indicates that samples with smaller loss are viewed as "easy" samples and thus should be processed first.

$$f(\mathbf{v}, \delta) = -\delta \sum_{m=1}^n v_m \quad (16)$$

The optimization of Eqs. (15) and (16) can be formulated as an alternative convex search (ACS) problem [55], in which variables are first classified into two blocks. Then, with one block fixed, the other block of variables can be optimized. This

operation is conducted in an iterative way. With the network parameter set Φ fixed, the optimal value for $\mathbf{v} = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n]$ can be obtained by:

$$v_m = \begin{cases} 1, & L(\mathbf{G}^{(m)}, g(\mathbf{I}^{(m)}; \Phi)) < \delta \\ 0, & otherwise \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

In each epoch, δ helps determine which training samples are allowed to participate in the label correction procedure. Denote the epoch as t , the threshold for t epoch as $\delta^{(t)}$ and the set of selected training samples as $\mathbf{S}^{(t)}$. In the set $\mathbf{S}^{(t)}$, $\mathbf{G}^{(t,m)}$, and $\mathbf{f}^{(t,m)}$ represent corresponding PLs and the output of the mapping network of the m^{th} training samples, respectively. For the selected training samples in the $t+1$ epoch, the output of the current mapping network is first binarized by the Otsu thresholding and then undergoes an opening operation with 9×9 structuring element \mathbf{SE} , which can help reduce the false positives in the training.

$$Mask^{(t,m)} = otsu(\mathbf{f}^{(t,m)}), \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{G}^{(t+1,m)} = Mask^{(t,m)} \circ \mathbf{SE} = (Mask^{(t,m)} \oplus \mathbf{SE}) \ominus \mathbf{SE}, \quad (19)$$

where \circ , \oplus , \ominus denotes the opening, dilation and erosion operation, respectively.

As the training phase goes, we relax the threshold thus a growing number of training samples with higher learning difficulties will be gradually appended into the label correction process.

$$\delta^{(t)} = \delta^{(0)} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{t}{\sigma}\right), \quad (20)$$

where $\delta^{(0)}$ is the predetermined threshold, and σ controls the pace of the growing difficulty.

The proposed self-paced label correction strategy is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: SP-LC strategy

Data: Input data set \mathcal{D} ;
 Initial pseudo labels by Grad-CAM $\mathbf{G}^{(0)}$;
 Initial threshold $\delta^{(0)}$;
 Pre-trained mapping network with parameter set $\Phi^{(0)}$
Result: Network parameter set Φ .

```

1 Initialize  $\mathbf{v}$  as  $\mathbf{v}^{(0)}$  ;
2  $t \leftarrow 0$  ;
3 while not converged do
4   Calculate  $\delta^{(t+1)}$  by Eq. (20);
5    $\mathbf{v}^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \underset{\mathbf{v}}{\operatorname{argmin}} \mathbb{E}(\Phi^{(t)}, \mathbf{v}; \delta^{(t+1)})$ ;
6   if  $v_m^{(t+1)}$  then
7     Update  $\mathbf{G}^{(t+1,m)}$  by Eqs. (18) and (19);
8   end
9    $\Phi^{(t+1)} \leftarrow \underset{\Phi}{\operatorname{argmin}} \mathbb{E}(\Phi, \mathbf{v}^{(t+1)}; \delta^{(t+1)})$ ;
10   $t \leftarrow t + 1$ ;
11 end
12 Return Network parameter set  $\Phi$ ;

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TABLE I
DETAILS OF THE GSM-ACT AND GMS-BRIS DATA SETS USED FOR EXPERIMENTS

Data set	Location	Resolution	Band	Size	Training set		Testing set		Unlabeled data
					Positive	Negative	Positive	Negative	
GSM-ACT	Canberra	0.15-0.3 m	RGB	256 × 256	437	414	98	92	3405
GSM-BRIS	Brisbane	0.3 m	RGB	256 × 256	457	676	99	117	5588

III. EXPERIMENTS

A. Data sets

To reveal the validity of the proposed method, we evaluate the performance of SP-RAN on two aerial data sets, i.e., GSM-ACT and GMS-BRIS, both of which were obtained with Google Static Map API. The GSM-ACT data set was collected in Canberra, ACT, Australia, with the spatial resolution varying from 0.15m to 0.3m. Regarding the training samples with image-level annotations, the training set of GSM-ACT contains 437 positive samples and 414 negative samples while the testing set consists of 98 positive samples and 92 negative samples. GSM-ACT data set is also equipped with 3405 unlabeled samples. Images in the GMS-BRIS data set were captured in Brisbane, QLD, Australia. In the GSM-BRIS, 457 positive samples and 676 negative samples are used for the training; 99 positive samples and 117 negative ones are employed for testing. The unlabelled data are composed of 5588 samples. All the images employed have the size of 256×256 pixels. Detailed information for the two data sets is summarized in Table I.

B. Implementation Details

The image-level classification network and target mapping network are trained separately in the training phase. The classification network based on VGG16 is utilized by Grad-CAM to produce initial PLs. The well-trained VGG16 is also used to produce classification scores for the confidence-aware loss, which is subsequently employed to train the target mapping network. In the testing phase, only the target mapping network is required.

For the classification network, we use the training set with image-level annotations, which reflect the existence of desired objects in an image. VGG16 is adopted as the backbone. As it is difficult to train VGG16 from scratch, we fine-tuned the pre-trained VGG16, with all the convolutional layers' weights initialized with the pre-trained model over the ImageNet datasets [56]. The weights of three FC layers are randomly initialized with a truncated normal distribution, where mean and standard deviation are set to 0 and 0.01, respectively. For both data sets, we use the cross-entropy to train the classification network with the RMSProp optimizer. The batch size is 16 and the learning rate is 10^{-4} . The training phase ends after 10 epochs.

The training of the target mapping network is composed of two stages: initial training with the training set, and incremental training with SP-LC and unlabeled data. Both training procedures use the Adam optimizer with a batch size of 8.

In the initial training, the initial learning rate is 10^{-3} and decreased by a factor of 0.8 after every 30 epochs for the GMS-BRIS data set and 0.9 after every 20 epochs for the GSM-ACT data set. This stage terminates after 200 epochs. In the incremental training, more positive samples are identified by the classification network from the unlabeled data and then Grad-CAM is utilized to produce PLs for the RAN. This stage takes 100 epochs with a learning rate of 10^{-5} .

For the gated CRF regularizer term of the confidence-aware loss, we set the window size $r = 11$, $w^{(1)} = 0.9$ and $w^{(2)} = 0.1$ in the two-kernel potential $k(\cdot, \cdot)$ for both data sets. On the GSM-ACT data set, the weight λ for balancing the WCE loss and the Gated CRF regularizer term is 0.3. θ_1 , θ_2 , and θ_3 is set as 6, 16, and 6. On the GMS-BRIS data set, we set $\lambda = 0.1$, $\theta_1 = 6$, $\theta_2 = 30$, and $\theta_3 = 6$, respectively.

In the SP-LC, threshold $\delta^{(0)}$ is selected according to the loss in the initial training stage. For the GSM-BRIS data set, $\delta^{(0)} = 0.02$ and $\sigma = 200$; for the GSM-ACT data set, $\delta^{(0)} = 0.04$ and $\sigma = 200$;

The proposed method was developed with publicly available Tensorflow framework and executed on NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPU with 32GB memory. The code is publicly available at <https://github.com/zhangjue1993/Weakly-Supervised-Solar-Panel-Mapping> (after the manuscript is accepted).

C. Comparison with the State-of-the-art

We compared the proposed SP-RAN with HWSL [39], WS-SOD [28], PSL [42], Grad-CAM [26], DeepSolar [44] and PS-CNNLC [32], which are state-of-the-art weakly supervised object segmentation methods proposed recently.

HWSL integrates class-specific multi-scale salient features generated by a well-trained classification network and obtain the segmentation results after a subtraction operation. WS-SOD uses an auxiliary edge detection branch and a gated structure-aware loss as constraints for the object structure and boundary. Inspired by curriculum learning, PSL first constructs a shallow feedback saliency analysis network for semantic segmentation and then adopts a new denoising loss function to mitigate the effect brought by missing judgment in initial PLs. DeepSolar extends class activation mapping with a greedy layer-wise training, aiming to find the precise outlines of solar panels. PS-CNNLC is a simple application of the alternative training scheme in weakly supervised solar panel mapping, in which Grad-CAM is first utilized to generate PLs and empirical constraints are employed to correct the PLs progressively. Although both PS-CNNLC and proposed SP-RAN adopt the alternative training scheme, SP-RAN is superior in the following aspects: first, SP-RAN resorts to

Fig. 5. Comparisons of mapping results on the GSM-ACT data set, marked with true positives (Yellow), true negatives (Black), false positives (Green) and false negatives (Red). (a) Original images. (b) HWSL. (c) WS-SOD. (d) PSL. (e) Grad-CAM. (f) DeepSolar. (g) PS-CNNLC. (h) SP-RAN.

TABLE II
QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION RESULTS ON THE GSM-ACT AND GSM-BRIS DATA SETS

Data set	Metric	HWSL	WS-SOD	PSL	Grad-CAM	DeepSolar	PS-CNNLC	SP-RAN
GSM-ACT	<i>Accuracy</i>	97.90%	98.40%	97.96%	98.98%	97.26%	98.59%	99.07%
	<i>Precision</i>	48.29%	56.98%	49.15%	75.55%	40.62%	60.70%	73.13%
	<i>Recall</i>	69.65%	82.60%	49.55%	72.34%	79.38%	83.93%	84.02%
	F_1	57.04%	67.43%	49.34%	73.91%	53.74%	70.45%	78.20%
	<i>IoU</i>	39.90%	50.87%	32.75%	58.62%	36.75%	54.38%	64.21%
GSM-BRIS	<i>Accuracy</i>	98.13%	97.82%	98.61%	98.66%	97.33%	97.68%	98.61%
	<i>Precision</i>	59.29%	53.49%	87.76%	74.45%	47.57%	52.82%	66.59%
	<i>Recall</i>	68.26%	91.51%	50.96%	69.85%	74.41%	61.05%	88.14%
	F_1	63.46%	67.52%	64.48%	72.08%	58.04%	56.63%	75.86%
	<i>IoU</i>	46.48%	50.96%	47.58%	56.35%	40.88%	39.50%	61.11%

a better-designed network architecture, in which the residual aggregated blocks are integrated with feature pyramid network to handle the large intra-class variations in remote sensing images. Then, rather than using the simple WCE loss, a new loss function, i.e., the confidence-aware loss is proposed, with confidence weighting introduced aiming to reduce the negative impacts of bad-quality PLs and gated CRF loss is also introduced to suppress the background. Finally, PS-CNNLC imposes three empirical constraints to help the label correction process, which inevitably introduces new falsely

labeled pixels and mixes irrelevant surroundings with the desired objects. The proposed SP-LC strategy mitigates this problem via dynamically selecting reliable results to update the PLs in the correction process.

Both visual and quantitative comparisons are presented as follows.

1) *Visual comparison*: The mapping results by different methods are shown in Figures 5 and 6. Results are marked with true positives (Yellow), true negatives (Black), false positives (Green), and false negatives (Red) to highlight the difference between the results.

Fig. 6. Comparisons of mapping results on the GSM-BRIS data set, marked with true positives (Yellow), true negatives (Black), false positives (Green) and false negatives (Red). (a) Original images. (b) HWSL. (c) WS-SOD. (d) PSL. (e) Grad-CAM. (f) DeepSolar. (g) PS-CNNLC. (h) SP-RAN.

TABLE III
ABLATION STUDY ON THE GSM-ACT AND GSM-BRIS DATA SETS.

Data set	GSM-ACT					GSM-BRIS				
	Metric	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F_1	IoU	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F_1
RAN (baseline)	98.35%	55.54%	87.97%	68.09%	51.62%	96.92%	44.37%	95.69%	60.63%	43.50%
w/o Confidence weighting	98.87%	68.15%	82.11%	74.48%	59.34%	98.52%	66.93%	79.45%	72.65%	57.05%
w/o Gated CRF regularizer	98.98%	69.97%	85.67%	77.02%	62.64%	98.48%	63.94%	89.05%	74.43%	59.28%
w/o CA loss	98.97%	73.21%	76.43%	74.79%	59.73%	98.39%	61.93%	90.96%	73.69%	58.34%
w/o Unlabeled data	98.98%	70.94%	83.48%	76.70%	62.21%	98.48%	63.74%	89.29%	74.39%	59.22%
w/o SP-LC	98.93%	69.00%	85.09%	76.20%	61.56%	98.34%	60.99%	91.35%	73.14%	57.66%
Proposed SP-RAN	99.07%	73.13%	84.02%	78.20%	64.21%	98.61%	66.59%	88.14%	75.86%	61.11%

As presented in the figures, we can see that WS-SOD can cover the complete content of the objects, but exhibits deficient background suppression ability, as a large part of the rooftops is mistaken as the foreground. HWSL provides a relatively accurate estimation of solar panels lay-out, however it introduces many false-positive regions (Green pixels) and false-negative ones (Red pixels). Grad-CAM only predicts parts of the objects and offers unsatisfactory results when there are multiple occurrences of objects in a single image. With a much shallow network architecture, PSL is prone to miss some targets, especially when it comes to small objects located in the complex background. DeepSolar has much fewer false negatives at the cost of increasing false positives. PS-

CNNLC also leveraged unlabeled data and label updating, and compared with the methods aforementioned, improvements can be observed in the boundary maintenance. By contrast, despite some scattered background noises, the proposed SP-RAN demonstrates a superior ability to locate solar panels accurately and discover the complete object areas with sharp boundaries. Especially, when multiple instances appear in the image, the SP-RAN substantially outperforms other methods in producing precise mapping results.

2) *Quantitative comparison:* Five evaluation metrics are used to quantitatively assess the performance of the SP-RAN, including overall Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F_1 score and Intersection over Union (IoU). Precision-recall curves

Fig. 7. PRCs of the proposed SP-RAN method and other approaches on (a) GSM-ACT and (b) GSM-BRIS data sets.

Fig. 8. PRCs of ablation study on (a) GSM-ACT and (b) GSM-BRIS data sets.

(PRCs) are also employed to conduct further assessment. For PRCs, varying thresholds are first utilized to transform the mapping results into binary maps, which are subsequently compared with the manually annotated Ground-truth to generate *Precision*, and *Recall*.

The numerical results are summarized in Table II, with the best results reported in bold (larger values indicate better quality). PRCs for different methods are presented in Figure 7. From the results, we can observe that our method achieves the best overall performance with 78.20% F_1 score and 64.21% IoU score on the GSM-ACT data set, and 75.86% F_1 score and 61.11% IoU score on the GSM-BRIS data set. WS-SOD exhibits high recall and relatively low precision, especially on the GSM-BRIS data set, which is consistent with the observation in the visual comparison part. Grad-CAM has a much better *Precision*, but fails to locate the multiple objects, thus exhibiting unsatisfactory performance in *Recall*. DeepSolar and PS-CNNLC give priority to discovering complete objects and reducing false alarms, respectively. Compared with the state-of-the-art methods aforementioned, SP-RAN achieves at least 3% improvement in F_1 score on both the GSM-ACT and GSM-BRIS data sets, which are considerable gains for the challenging weakly supervised object segmentation task.

D. Ablation Study

We also carried out experiments to investigate how the Grad-CAM at different convolutional layers, confidence-aware loss, unlabeled data, SP-LC strategy, and residual aggregation architecture benefit the proposed method. The results of the ablation study are reported in Tables III, IV, V and Figure 8. The RAN trained with the training set and WCE loss is the baseline of our work.

1) *Influence of the the Grad-CAM at different convolutional layers*: Figure 9 shows how localizations change qualitatively as we performed Grad-CAM with respect to different feature maps in the classification network. We can see that the best localization are usually obtained with the deeper convolutional layer in the network, and Grad-CAM performs worse at shallower layers. It is noteworthy that with the shallow layer conv3_3, Grad-CAM sometimes fails to localize the targets, with the activation maps corrupted by a large amount of noise; with the deeper layer conv5_3, a large proportion of rooftops are taken as the desired objects by mistake. To reveal the difference quantitatively, we generated activation maps with conv3_3, conv4_3, and conv5_3 and used the PLs to train the proposed SP-RAN. Quantitative results are shown in Table IV. We can see that on both data sets, SP-RAN with conv4_3 provides superior performance. The employment of conv5_3 helps improve the recall but leads to much worse precision.

2) *Impact of the confidence-aware loss*: To reveal the contribution of the confidence-aware loss, we implemented three ablation experiments to show the improvement brought by the confidence weighting and the gated CRF regularizer term. “w/o CA loss” denotes the SP-RAN trained with only WCE loss; “w/o Confidence weighting” denotes the SP-RAN trained with the WCE loss and gated CRF regularizer term [as shown in Eq. (21)]; “w/o Gated CRF regularizer” denotes the SP-RAN trained with confidence-weighted WCE loss [as shown in Eq. (22)].

$$L = \sum_m L_{wce}^{(m)} + \lambda L_{crf}^{(m)} \quad (21)$$

$$L = \sum_m f(\mathbf{I}; \Theta)_{c=1}^{(m)} \cdot L_{wce}^{(m)} \quad (22)$$

TABLE IV
QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION RESULTS WITH GRAD-CAM AT DIFFERENT LAYERS ON THE GSM-ACT AND GSM-BRIS DATA SETS

Data set	Metric	w/ conv3_3	w/ conv4_3	w/ conv5_3
GSM-ACT	Accuracy	98.55%	99.07%	95.34%
	Precision	65.05%	73.13%	28.18%
	Recall	60.28%	84.02%	85.42%
	F_1	62.57%	78.20%	42.38%
	IoU	45.53%	64.21%	26.89%
GSM-BRIS	Accuracy	98.36%	98.61%	97.94%
	Precision	63.61%	66.59%	55.04%
	Recall	79.07%	88.14%	93.27%
	F_1	70.51%	75.86%	69.22%
	IoU	54.45%	61.11%	52.93%

TABLE V
COMPARISON OF THE PERFORMANCE WITH DIFFERENT BACKBONES ON GSM-ACT AND GSM-BRIS DATA SETS.

Data set	GSM-ACT					GSM-BRIS				
	<i>Accuracy</i>	<i>Precision</i>	<i>Recall</i>	F_1	<i>IoU</i>	<i>Accuracy</i>	<i>Precision</i>	<i>Recall</i>	F_1	<i>IoU</i>
w/ U-net	98.89%	69.94%	78.21%	73.84%	58.53%	98.14%	58.19%	88.54%	70.22%	54.11%
w/ FPN	98.21%	53.51%	80.44%	64.27%	47.35%	97.87%	54.05%	93.85%	68.60%	52.20%
w/ RAN	99.07%	73.13%	84.02%	78.20%	64.21%	98.61%	66.59%	88.14%	75.86%	61.11%

Fig. 9. Grad-CAM at different convolutional layers in the classification network. First row: Original images with solar panels remarked by red lines; second row: activation maps with conv3_3; third row: activation maps with conv4_3; fourth row: activation maps with conv5_3.

As shown in Table III, the confidence weighting effectively increases the *Recall* (82.11% vs 84.02% on the GSM-ACT; 79.45% vs 88.14% on the GSM-BRIS) while the Gated CRF regularizer significantly helps the model reduce false alarms and achieve higher *Precision* (69.97% vs 73.13% on the GSM-ACT; 63.94% vs 66.59% on the GSM-BRIS). The confidence-aware loss combines the benefits of the two strategies and helps boost the overall performance, with the F_1 score increased by 3.41% and 2.17%, respectively.

3) *Learning with unlabeled data*: We utilized the unlabeled data as auxiliary information to improve the generalization ability of the model. To verify the importance of the unlabeled data, we trained RAN with the confidence-aware loss and only the training set shown in Table I, which is denoted as “w/o Unlabeled data”. Comparing with the performance of “w/o Unlabeled data”, “Proposed SP-RAN” outperforms “w/o Unlabeled data” with considerable increases in *Accuracy*, F_1 score and *IoU* score. On the GSM-ACT data set, the employment of unlabeled data obtains 1.50% and 2.0% gain on the F_1 score and *IoU* score; the figures are 1.47% and 1.89% for the GSM-BRIS data set.

4) *Training with the SP-LC strategy*: To reveal the effectiveness of the proposed SP-LC strategy, we further carried out an ablation experiment without the SP-LC strategy, which

is shown as “w/o SP-LC” in Table III. It is noticeable that the application of the SP-LC strategy improves the *Precision* remarkably (4.13% and 5.6% on GSM-ACT and GSM-BRIS data sets, respectively) at the cost of a slight decline in *Recall* (1.07% and 3.21% on GSM-ACT and GSM-BRIS data sets, respectively). In general, SP-LC further boosts the performance by 2% and 2.72% F_1 score on GSM-ACT and GSM-BRIS data sets, respectively.

5) *Contribution of the RAN*: To reveal the contribution of the RAN, we replace the proposed target mapping network with two state-of-the-art networks, i.e., U-net and FPN, and keep the rest the same as proposed SP-RAN, to show the difference. In the Table V, the performance is denoted as “w/ RAN”, “w/ U-net” and “w/ FPN”, respectively. It is noteworthy that as the FPN is the backbone of the RAN, the comparison between “w/ RAN” and “w/ FPN” can substantially demonstrate the advantages of the residual aggregated architecture. From Table V, we can see that compared with U-net, RAN improves the performance of the target mapping network by significant margins on all the metrics; compared with FPN, RAN provides much better performance in reducing false alarms as well as considerable improvement in the ability to discover true positives. This strongly supports the validity of the residual aggregated architecture.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed an effective method for weakly supervised object extraction and applied it to the solar panel mapping in aerial images. With the confidence-aware loss and self-paced label correction strategy, the proposed method emphasizes the contribution of the high-quality PLs to the model training and minimizes the negative impacts of the bad-quality ones. The confidence-aware loss employs the classification score to adjust the contribution of training samples with quality-inconsistent PLs adaptively. Then, the self-paced label correction selects training samples with certain learning difficulties, which match the current model capacity, and updates their PLs instead of updating the entire set. Moreover, we proposed a residual aggregated network for target mapping, which aims at capturing complete objects with precise boundaries. Extensive experiments, as well as the ablation study on two aerial data sets, demonstrate the advantages of the proposed method.

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